

FEATURES OF CURRENT TOURISM MARKETING DEVELOPMENT

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Annotation: *This article discusses ways to develop and improve tourism marketing.*

Keywords: *tourism marketing, tourism products, tourism industry*

Annotatsiya: *Ushbu maqolada turizm marketingini rivojlantirish va takomillashtirish yo'llari yoritilgan .*

Kalit so'zlar: *turizm marketingi, turistik mahsulot, turizm industriyasi*

Аннотация: *В данной статье рассматриваются пути развития и совершенствования туристического маркетинга.*

Ключевые слова: *туристический маркетинг, туристический продукт, индустрия туризма.*

Introduction. Tourism marketing consists of systematic and unified actions to meet the needs (optimization) of national tourism organizations or tourism institutions, tourists at the national and international levels. The desire and need of people to travel to a region, country, or country for work, family, or conference purposes in order to value their free time has led to the establishment of tourism enterprises. These businesses are developing a variety of styles and techniques to help consumer groups travel to the most suitable locations and conditions. Another definition of tourism marketing is as follows:

"Tourism marketing is the sum of the activities of a producer and consumer of tourist products and services at the local, regional, national and international levels through the creation of new tourist consumption needs and proposals." Tourism marketing is the process of providing and selling products and services that meet the needs of tourists. The goal of hotels is to meet the needs of customers and satisfy them while making a profit.

Marketing is an ongoing process. Tourism products and services are sold to tourists directly by tourism companies or through intermediary firms, travel agencies or tour operators. The new needs of tourists in tourism marketing should be constantly explored and studied. The needs of the tourist are kept in the foreground. The fact that tourism carries significant features over other products or

services has made the use of marketing in this area much needed. A tourism product, unlike other goods and services, has the characteristics of a finished product rather than other establishments. The demand for tourism products is also sensitive to social and political changes and shows great resilience. The non-transportation (hotel) nature of the tourism offer results in the on-site termination of tourist services. At the end of the tourist season, hotels, planes and some other facilities cannot be transported to another area. The goals of tourism marketing activities can be grouped into 3 groups according to the main marketing objectives:

a) maintaining the existing market, in other words, keeping at least the same level of demand for tourism directed to the enterprise or country;

(b) Transforming potential market demand into a dynamic form of demand, that is, attracting organizations that have the capacity to participate in tourism, but have not yet been able to do so;

(c) the creation of new markets, access to previously unknown, unexplored or undervalued markets, and the expansion of tourism sales by attracting tourism demand to other enterprises or countries.

In recent years, economic changes and the development of new techniques have led to significant changes in the marketing forms and management of enterprises' services and products. Advances in computer technology have pushed some tourist distances to the forefront. Changes in consumer attitudes and other factors have led business owners to realize that customer waiting times are over, and that they now need to go out and look for customers and attract them. This process also applies to travel agencies such as restaurants or hotels.

There are only 3 important factors in changing the concept of marketing. [1]

1. The transition from the sum of production to the sum of consumption (when demand is less than supply) when only what is needed for production (if demand exceeds supply). In this case, the sales function is the first in the hotel sector. At this time, it is necessary to produce and distribute according to the needs of the market. On the other hand, it is becoming difficult to adapt to demand. This transition is a testament to the evolution of marketing.

2. The development of competition is the competition (product competition) that occurs between businesses that offer similar or value-added products or are in the same category, such as Hilton-Sheraton hotels or fast food establishments such as Mas Donald and Wath Hamburger. Competition between businesses from different sectors that offer similar products: merged hotel chains, volunteer chains, social tourism target sectors, and other groupings. Competition from the national market to the international market. At this level, even national competition has to

sacrifice itself in order to compete in the world. Foreign tourists have the right to choose from several distances: London, Paris, Rome, Brussels, Madrid, Turkey, Istanbul, Izmir, Antalya.

3. Changes and updates: In life - updates, practical applications, rising living standards, increasing the chances of consumers to choose between eating, sleeping and positive habits

Tourism marketing has some features similar to marketing in industrial enterprises. The features that distinguish tourism marketing from other industrial products are explained as follows: [2]

1. In the tourism industry, services are marketed and services do not have a material nature. However, industrial products are ideally measured or so-called tools.

2. Potential consumption is marketed in 2 different ways as opposed to products and services.

a) marketing carried out by official tourism organizations and not for direct sale;

b) marketing done by enterprises and aimed at selling their products.

Tourism marketing takes into account environmental issues more than industrial marketing. The sea, the sand, the sun, the presence and richness of natural beauties affect marketing.

3. In tourism marketing, the consumer goes to the place of production to receive the service, while in industrial marketing, the products are brought and delivered from the producer to the consumer.

4. In tourism marketing, production and consumption occur at the same time. Services are pre-purchased, while products produced in industrial marketing are offered for sale.

5. Tourism enterprises operate seasonally. Tourism services are not durable and long-lasting services.

6. There is little dependence on the brand (label) regulations in the tourism industry. The real product in the tourism market is a region or cultural center with high attraction.

7. The created demand for tourist services is daily, weekly, monthly and annual demand. Demand is elastic.

8. The main goal of tourism marketing is to satisfy the consumer.

9. The purpose of industrial marketing is to benefit a product from a consumer.

10. Tourism products are mainly provided in the form of customer service.

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11. A tourism product is a pure service product that differs only in its use.
 12. Tourism products are mixed products.
 13. Tourist products are not collected. Therefore, tourism marketing is a risk.
 14. It is not possible to standardize tourism products because they are different from each other.
 15. Tourism products are finished products.
 16. The control function is very difficult because tourism products are mixed products.
 17. Tourism marketing is more risky than industrial marketing. Unless a restaurant or hotel is for sale, you will not be able to move it to another location.
 18. The purchase and use of a service creates the right relationship between the consumer and the manufacturer. The results are as follows.
 - a) The situation in which this relationship occurs is very important. The corridor of a hotel, the interior of a restaurant, is the result of the expected service.
 - b) there is a high degree of individuality in the relationship. A customer of a famous big hotel or restaurant will feel a great joy when they are called or remembered by name there. Otherwise, the tourist may not come here again.

ConclusionThe development of tourism is unimaginable without marketing. Because marketing plays a key role in the study of the tourism market. However, marketing services in the tourism system of the country are not well established. To do this, it is necessary to study foreign tourism markets and try to sell national tourism products there. At present, the demand for our national products is moderate, but the pricing policy is not good. Prices are much higher than products from the world market. Therefore, the demand of tourists is declining. They are visiting for organizational purposes only.

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